

USE OF MSCT EXAMINATION IN DIFFUSE LIVER DISEASES

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Annotation: More than 350 million people worldwide are infected with hepatitis viruses. Each year, millions of people are newly infected with viruses causing liver diseases, including hepatitis B and hepatitis C, leading to life-threatening conditions. Liver cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma are consequences of chronic hepatitis B and C infections.

Introduction: *Liver diseases affect up to 2 million people annually globally, with 1 million suffering from cirrhosis-related complications and another 1 million facing viral hepatitis and hepatocellular carcinoma. Cirrhosis accounts for 3.5% of all deaths worldwide, ranking 11th among the leading causes of death due to various factors.

"Improving the radiological diagnosis of diffuse liver diseases associated with cirrhosis."

"The tasks of scientific work"

1. Determine the importance of CT scanning in diagnosing the clinical manifestations and stages of diffuse liver diseases.
2. Identify the characteristics of contrast-enhanced CT scanning for diffuse liver diseases based on stage and type of disease.
3. Identify typical imaging syndromes for diffuse liver diseases.
4. Analyze the diagnostic informativeness of CT scanning in patients with various types of diffuse liver diseases.

"Materials and methods"

Total number of patients - 50.

The primary materials were collected from the Department of Hepatology and Clinical Archives of Tashkent Medical Academy.

Examination methods:

Neusoft Newvision 16-slice CT scanner.

The distribution of patients according to age.

Age	Nosological forms										Jami (M = 50)	
	Viral Hepatitis n=21				Cirrhosis stages n=29							
	Hepatitis B (n = 9)		Hepatitis C (n = 12)		A (n - 8)		B (n = 11)		C (n = 10)			
	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	Abs.	%
18-20	1	2	2	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	6
21-30	3	6	2	4	1	2	2	4	2	4	10	20

31-40	2	4	4	8	2	4	1	2	1	2	10	20
41-50	1	2	2	4	2	4	3	6	3	6	11	22
51-60	1	2	1	2	2	4	2	4	2	4	8	16
61-70	1	2	-	-	1	2	3	6	2	4	7	14
Over 70	-	-	1	2	-	-	-	-	1	2	2	4
Total	9	18	12	24	8	16	11	22	10	20	50	100,0

"The diagnostic accuracy of liver contour changes syndrome on CT scan"

	Se		Sp		Ac		p	
	Hepatitis	Cirrhosis	Hepatitis	Cirrhosis	Hepatitis	Cirrhosis	Hepatitis	Cirrhosis
MSKT	82,3	90,1	96,8	99,3	88,4	95,2	<0,05	<0,05

"In 35 patients (70%), changes in liver contour were identified, with liver edge blunting (n = 19) and liver capsule retraction (n = 16) being the most common findings. These features were predominantly observed in patients with cirrhosis (29 individuals)."
Change in liver contours. The patient is 47 years old. Liver edges appear irregular on the CT scan.

The number of patients with changes in liver size	"Nosological types"											p
	Hepatitis (n= 21)		"Cirrhosis stages"						Jami (n= 50)			
			A (n = 8)		B (n = 11)		C (n = 10)					
	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	Abs.	%		
Enlargement of the right lobe	2	4	3	6	7	14	7	14	19	38	p < 0,05	
"Enlargement of the left lobe"	-	-	1	2	4	8	6	12	11	22	p < 0,05	
"Enlargement of the caudate lobe"	-	-	1	2	7	14	8	16	16	32	p < 0,05	
Total	2	4	5	10	17	34	18	36	46	92	p < 0,05	

The number of patients with changes in liver size	"Nosological types"											p
	"Hepatitis" (n= 21)		"Cirrhosis stages"						"Total" (n= 50)			
			A (n = 8)		B (n = 11)		C (n = 10)					
	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	Abs.	%		
"Reduction of the right lobe"	-	-	3	6	5	10	7	14	15	30	p < 0,05	
"Reduction of the left lobe"	-	-	-	-	2	4	3	6	5	10	p < 0,05	
"Reduction of the caudate lobe"	-	-	1	2	3	6	5	10	9	18	p < 0,05	
Total	-	-	4	8	10	20	15	30	29	58	p < 0,05	

Change in liver size syndrome on CT scan.

Change in liver size syndrome on CT scan.

In patients with hepatitis, the liver volume was normal in 19 cases (38%).

Information from CT scans in cirrhosis differs by stage:

- 14 patients (28%) showed no changes in liver size.
- Among patients with cirrhosis in stage A, 1 (2%) had a decrease in liver size, in stage B, 3 (6%) had a decrease, and in stage C, 5 (10%) showed a narrowing of the hepatic vein trunk.

In patients with cirrhosis in stage C, due to the disproportionate nature of the lesions, the liver appears to be "tilted" towards the anterior direction based on the direction of the liver's hour hand:

Change in liver size on CT scan. The patient is 35 years old, presenting with marked hepatomegaly.

Change in liver density syndrome on CT scan.

"The number of patients"	"Nozological forms"										Total (N = 50)	
	Hepatitis				Cirrhosis stages							
	B (n = 9)		C(n = 12)		A(n = 8)		B (n = 11)		C(n = 10)		Abs.	%
	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	Abs.	%		

"Density decrease"	-	-	1	2	1	2	-	-	-	-	2	4
"Density increase"	-	-	-	-	4	8	8	16	8	16	20	40
"Atypical density change"	-		1	2	3	6	3	6	2	4	9	18
Total			2	4	8	16	11	22	10	20	31	62

Changes in liver density syndrome on CT scan.

In patients with hepatitis, changes in liver density were not observed significantly. However, in 2 patients with hepatitis C, a decrease in density was noted.

In cirrhosis cases, an increase in liver density was mainly observed. Liver density increased as the cirrhosis stage progressed.

In the syndrome of biliary system changes on CT scan.

Changes identified in the CT scan examination include:

- Homogeneity of bile ducts in 14 (28%) patients,
- Dilatation of the bile duct up to 60 HB in 32 (64%) patients,
- Presence of concrements in the bile ducts in 18 (32%) patients.

The CT scan provided a clear visualization of the common bile duct and the gallbladder, allowing visualization of gas in the lumen of the common bile duct and the gallbladder.

Splenomegaly syndrome on CT scan.

Splenomegaly was identified in 7 patients with hepatitis B and 8 patients with hepatitis C, totaling 15 individuals. In cirrhosis, splenomegaly was identified in 2 patients at stage B and 3 patients at stage C.

	Se		Sp		Ac		p	
	Hepatitis	Cirrhosis	Hepatitis	Cirrhosis	Hepatitis	Cirrhosis	Hepatitis	Cirrhosis
MSKT	79,9	86,5	81,2	85,1	88,4	95,2	<0,05	<0,05

In the syndrome of splenomegaly on CT scan, the spleen appears enlarged.

1	4	5
0,1	8	3
0,1	8	2

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Ascites syndrome on CT scan.

In the CT scan examination, ascites was identified in a total of 25 patients: 6 in stage A cirrhosis, 9 in stage B cirrhosis, and 10 in stage C cirrhosis. It was determined that the minimum amount of fluid detected in the abdominal cavity on CT scan was 150 ml.

	Se		Sp	Ac	p

	Cirrhosis		Cirrhosis	Cirrhosis	Cirrhosis
MSKT	88,9		87,1	95,2	<0,05

In ascites syndrome on CT scan, the patient, aged 55, presents with ascites associated with stage C cirrhosis.

Contrast-enhanced CT scan examination for diffuse liver diseases. The patient, aged 45, is in stage A cirrhosis (Child-Pugh classification).

Summary

1. Various imaging methods can be used to diagnose diffuse liver diseases, but contrast-enhanced CT scanning is highly reliable.

2. The effectiveness of contrast-enhanced CT scanning in diagnosing both diffuse hepatitis and liver cirrhosis is over 85.0%. This demonstrates the importance of imaging in diagnosing hepatitis with approximately 85.0% accuracy and cirrhosis with about 95.0% accuracy.

3. The semiotics of diffuse liver diseases are characterized by a wide range of imaging variations. The following imaging syndromes are most characteristic: changes in liver contours (seen in 70.0% of patients with general liver diseases), splenomegaly (40.0%), changes in liver volume (76.0%), presence of ascites in patients with cirrhosis (86.2%), and changes in bile ducts (80.0%). The correlation of syndromes developed in the JDK imaging is important for identifying the stage of liver damage.

4. In the JDK imaging, CT scanning exhibits high sensitivity, specificity, and diagnostic accuracy: $Sp = 75.0\%$, $Se = 93.0\%$, $Ac = 88.0\%$.

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